

Amino-OPEs Glycosides and Blue Light: A Powerful Synergy in Photodynamic Therapy

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ABSTRACT

Herein we report the synthesis and biological properties of sugar-conjugated Oligophenylene ethynyls (OPEs) dyes, as novel photosensitizers (PS) for photodynamic treatment (PDT) under blue light. The OPEs bearing glycosides at both ends are successfully prepared by a Pd-catalyzed Sonogashira cross-coupling reaction. The live-cell imaging studies shown that these OPE glycosides (including glucose, mannose and maltose derivative) efficiently penetrate in the cytoplasm of cultured cancer HeLa cells. No dark toxicity was observed, but irradiating the cells under blue light an extraordinary photodynamic effect was obtained at low concentrations (10^{-6} - 10^{-8} M). The localization studies indicates that OPE-glucose **1** and OPE-Mannose **2** have a Golgi patterns, whereas OPE-maltose **3** could be in lysosomes. The PDT and morphological studies in HeLa cells treated with sublethal doses of PS **1-3**, revealed that cell death occurs by necrosis.

Introduction

The sequence of aromatic rings and ethynyl moieties in Oligophenylene ethynylenes, known as OPEs, creates a stable π -electron conjugation, thus rendering them intrinsically luminescent dyes.¹ They are characterized by an absorption maximum at $\lambda_{\text{max}} \sim 400$ nm, which can be tuned, as for the emission wavelength, by the variation of the aromatic units and/or the substituents:^{2, 3} a higher number of aromatic rings and the presence of donor substituents usually lead to bathochromic shifts of the absorption; on the other hand, acceptor moieties are less effective in the tuning of these properties; the combination of electron donating and electron withdrawing groups in the same skeleton strongly influences the photophysical properties of the OPEs.⁴ Their tunable spectroscopic and electronic properties depend not only on their molecular structure, but also on the supramolecular interactions and on the aggregation of the chains both in solution and in the solid state.⁵ Little changes in OPEs length and/or monomer composition, the decoration of the two extremities and of the core of the conjugated chain with the insertion of suitable different chains and/or end groups helps their chemical and physical properties (e.g. solubility, columbic and/or hydrophobic interactions, solvent quenching effects etc.), modulates their interaction with target molecules deeply influencing their spectral behavior, and allowing their use as sensors or as probes. As a consequence, these effects permit precise interpretations of their actions in biology and definite applications in medical fields. Suitable and definite structures can be projected to enter a cell and act as biocompatible fluorescent probes directed towards target organelles, to behave as antimicrobial and antiviral compounds, as labelling agents, as fluorescence turn-on system for the detection of little molecules, in drug delivery systems and in photodynamic therapy (PDT).⁶ This non-invasive therapeutic technique,^{7, 8} employed in the medical field, exploits the combination of light with photo-activable drugs (not toxic in the dark), called-photosensitizers (PSs). The process starts with the administration of PS to a cancerous tissue, followed by the exposure to light of specific wavelength that activates the short-lived excited singlet state (S1) of the accumulated drug. The excited species can then decay to the ground state or undergo intersystem crossing to the long-lived triplet state (T1), causing the interaction with the surrounding

molecular species and generating cytotoxic free radicals and/or singlet oxygen ($^1\text{O}_2$). PDT-mediated oxidative cytotoxicity induces tumor tissue destruction via cell apoptosis or necrosis, vascular damage, and inflammation-mediated immune compartment.^{9, 10} As $^1\text{O}_2$ has a very short half-life, the primary targets of PDT must be located very close to the PS, otherwise photodamage will not occur.^{11, 12} Various cell compartments can be damaged after PDT irradiation: plasma membrane, lysosomes, mitochondria, the Golgi apparatus, the endoplasmic reticulum, nuclear DNA, and also components of the cytoskeleton and cell adhesion molecules. Recently, a huge number of scientific works report PSs derivatized with monoclonal antibodies,¹³ peptides and proteins,¹⁴ folic acid,¹⁵ mono- and disaccharides¹⁶ that can control and help the PS ability to target specific tissues and direct the localization in definite cell compartments.¹⁷

The use of carbohydrates in biological science^{18, 19} relies on their unique features like aqueous solubility, biocompatibility and biodegradability, good cell internalization capability, specific targeting of cell-membrane proteins. Mono- or disaccharides can be exploited to build-up glycoconjugates drugs,^{20, 21} less toxic than the parent aglycons,²² that can selectively target and localize a drug in a specific site of action (glyco-targeting).²³ Glucose transporters (GLUTs), located on membranes of endothelial cells and overexpressed in human cancers are the responsible of the diffusion of glucose and other carbohydrates into tumor cells (Warburg effect):²⁴ they represent the target of D-glucose²⁵ and D-galactose-conjugated medicines,²⁶ being L-glucose completely inactive²⁷ and D-galactose-conjugated drugs selectively targeting²⁸ breast and colon cancers. D-mannose and D-galactose exhibit the highest affinity for target lectins,²⁹ a protein widely distributed in viruses and bacteria which is able to reversibly and specifically bind mono- and disaccharides. Despite different sugars show their specificity and can be utilized in drug design, the aim to rational select a suitable saccharide for the targeting of a specific drug has not been reached yet. Our group previously reported the combination of a dimethylamino or trimethylammonium groups on the aromatic functions of a conjugated chain of OPEs having two glucose-end terminations as biocompatible³⁰ OPEs derivatives with good applications in bioimaging,³¹ PDT using UV-vis light³² and turn-off sensors in DNA

interactions.³³ Inspired by this work and giving the importance of carbohydrate structures in biological targeting, we envisioned the synthesis of new amino-OPE derivatives, side-ended with two different pairs of glycosides, such as mannose and maltose. The biological studies conducted in HeLa cells revealed an outstanding behavior of these sugar-OPEs, including the glucose derivative, as PS for PDT at very low concentrations using less harmful visible (blue) light as a source of illumination.

Results and discussion – SYNTHESIS

In previous studies, we made several important observations about the photophysical and photodynamic behavior of OPE-Glucose **1** derivative, determining that the central dimethylamino aryl substituent confined by the two-dimethoxyphenylethenyl units gave the best results in terms of $^1\text{O}_2$ production. In this report, we show that mannose and maltose derivatives (OPE-Mannose **2** and OPE-Maltose **3**), possessing the same internal OPE chain, can be used as lysosomal or Golgi fluorescent probes for PDT experiments in HeLa cells under blue light irradiation. Moreover, these cell permeable probes are non-cytotoxic under dark conditions and present good photostability and large Stokes shifts.³⁴

Figure 1

OPE-Mannose **2** and OPE-Maltose **3** were prepared in a three-step synthesis from commercially available α -D-mannose pentaacetate **4a** and α -D-maltose octaacetate **4b** by first reaction with propargyl alcohol, in the presence of TMSOTf as a Lewis acid, to give the corresponding propargyl acetals **5a**³⁵ and **5b**³⁶ (Scheme 1). Next, Pd(0)-mediated Heck-Cassar-Sonogashira coupling of **5a** or **5b**, in the presence of twofold 1,4-dimethoxy-2,5-diiodobenzene, afforded **7a** and **7b**, still containing a the iodoaryl termination. The diiodo compound **6** was used in molar excess in order to minimize the formation of the bis-sugar-substituted aromatic ring, the excess of **6** was easily removed by precipitation from cold MeOH. Undesired bis-adducts were inevitably obtained as minor by-products, but readily separated from the respective **7a** and **7b**, by simple column chromatography, giving the desired compounds in good yields and in pure form, as white solids.

The sugar-containing OPE **7a** and **7b**, were next coupled with the dimethylamino derivative **8**, coming from the K₂CO₃-mediated quantitative desilylation of the already reported trimethylsilyl derivative **9**.³⁷ The Sonogashira cross-coupling reaction between **7a** or **7b** with the aromatic core **8** proceeded smoothly to give **10a** and **10b** isolated pure in 77% and 74% yields respectively. It should be pointed out that this protocol is more efficient than the formal Ag₂O-mediated reaction previously described for the analogous derivative **1**³¹ that required harsher conditions. Final deacetylation of **10a** and **10b** afforded OPE-Mannose **2** and OPE-Maltose **3** as bright yellow solids, in quantitative yields.

Scheme 1

Both the absorption and the emission spectra of OPE-Mannose **2** and OPE-Maltose **3** were similar to those exhibited by the glucose derivative **1**. All three species showed an emission band centered at 502 nm upon excitation at 375 nm (10^{-5} M in water), with a Stokes shift of 127 nm (see Figure S11 and S12).

Biological study. Dark Toxicity

The potentiality of the new synthesized OPEs conjugated as photosensitizers was tested using HeLa cells as an *in vitro* model of cancer cells. The cytotoxic activity of the conjugates was evaluated using the MTT assay to study the cytotoxic effect of these compounds in the absence of light. For this purpose, different concentrations of OPEs conjugates **1-3** (from 3×10^{-8} M to 3×10^{-5} M) were administered to cell cultures in the dark, for a period of 18 h. Survival rates obtained at 24 h after treatment (Table 1) showed no alterations in cell viability at 3×10^{-8} M and 3×10^{-7} M concentrations,

as their values were similar to those of total control. However, with highest concentrations of 10^{-5} M and 10^{-6} M, a decrease in cell viability, between 1% and 20%, could be observed.

Table 1. Percentage of survival of HeLa cells incubated in the dark 18 h at different concentrations of compounds OPE-Glucose **1**, OPE-Mannose **2** and OPE-Maltose **3**.

[PS]	HeLa		
	OPE-Glucose 1	OPE-Mannose 2	OPE-Maltose 3
Control	101.06 ± 2.18	99.41 ± 6.14	101.20 ± 5.44
3×10^{-8} M	101.36 ± 1.17	100.82 ± 3.75	100.58 ± 5.47
3×10^{-7} M	101.08 ± 1.18	100.48 ± 6.73	100.26 ± 9.56
3×10^{-6} M	89.32 ± 4.97	99.92 ± 3.98	96.89 ± 2.22
3×10^{-5} M	83.64 ± 2.73	80.30 ± 3.59	79.82 ± 3.28

Each point corresponds to the mean value ± SD from three different experiments

Subcellular localization

The efficiency of a photosensitizer is highly dependent on its subcellular location. The diffusion length and lifetime of singlet oxygen are very short (0.1 nm and 0.5 ms, respectively),³⁸ consequently initial oxidative reactions occur in organelles or membrane structures in which the photosensitizers are found and also in other cell structures, bringing all together to cell photodamage.³⁹ The subcellular localization of the OPE compounds incubated in HeLa cells for 24 h, were determined by their green emission under fluorescence microscopy, using ultraviolet or blue light channels. OPE-glucose **1** and OPE-mannose **2** (Figure 2A and B) showed a green emission fluorescence pattern in a juxtannuclear region whereas the OPE-maltose **3** (Figure 2C) green signal is localized in the form of cytoplasm granules that closely resemble lysosomes. In all the three cases, the signal of these compounds clearly differs from the mitochondrial signal observed under UV light (Figure 2A, B and C; UV).

Figure 2. Subcellular localization of OPE-Glucose **1** (A), OPE-mannose **2** (B) and OPE-Maltose **3** (C) in HeLa cells. Under UV light, the autofluorescent signal of the mitochondria is observed in all cases. A stronger green signal appears in treated cells, under UV light and blue light. Scale bar: 20 μ m.

Based on these results, we can conclude that both OPE-glucose **1** and OPE-mannose **2** show similar localization patterns in HeLa cells resembling Golgi network, while the location of the OPE-maltose **3** could be in lysosomes.

Cell viability and ROS production

We next analyzed the photodynamic effect of the OPE-sugar conjugates. HeLa cells were incubated for 18 h using different concentrations (10^{-6} , 10^{-7} and 10^{-8} M) of OPE conjugates and then were irradiated under blue light for 1, 3, 5 and 10 min. Control experiments (Total control (TC): untreated cells and Light control (LC): cells without drug and irradiated under blue light) were also conducted. The cell survival percentages (Figure 3) were measured by the MTT assay. A clear cytotoxic effect was observed for the OPE-treated cells depending on the concentration and the irradiation time. Concentrations of 3×10^{-6} M for both Glucose **1** and Mannose **2** caused a lethality rate of over 80% at all times of irradiation. In the case of OPE-Glucose **1**, a concentration of 3×10^{-8} M caused slight phototoxicity at all times analyzed, whereas values of 50% cell survival (sublethal treatment) could be obtained at 3×10^{-7} M, between 1 and 3 min of irradiation (Figure 3A). Remarkably, OPE-Mannose **2** was able to generate toxicity values of 40% at the lowest concentration (3×10^{-8} M) after 10 min of

irradiation, whereas a concentration of 3×10^{-7} M induced survival rates of 40% after 1 min of irradiation (Figure 3B). In the case of OPE-Maltose **3**, values greater than 90% of cell survival were obtained after cell treatment with 5×10^{-7} M and 5×10^{-8} M at all times analyzed. Sublethal treatment could only be obtained at a concentration of 5×10^{-6} M between 1 and 3 min of blue light irradiation (Figure 3C).

Figure 3. Cell survival rates after (A) OPE-Glucose **1**, (B) OPE-Mannose **2** and (C) OPE-Maltose **3** based blue light PDT. HeLa cells were incubated 18 h with 3×10^{-6} M, 3×10^{-7} M and 3×10^{-8} M of OPE- **1** and **2** and 5×10^{-6} M, 5×10^{-7} M and 5×10^{-8} M of OPE **3**. A clear cytotoxic effect was observed for the OPE-treated cells depending on the concentration of the PS and the irradiation time. Each point corresponds to the mean value \pm SD from three different experiments.

All these findings indicated that OPE compounds were not toxic to HeLa cells in the absence of light at concentrations below 3×10^{-7} M, and the cytotoxic effect observed under blue light irradiation study can be attributed to the production of reactive oxygen species (ROS).

To investigate whether intracellular ROS is involved in OPE-PDT mediated cell death, we next measured the level of ROS within the cells using DCF (2,7-dichlorofluorescein) as a fluorometric probe able to detect a wide range of ROS by fluorescence microscopy. The production of ROS in HeLa cells was initially tested using HeLa cells treated with OPE-Mannose **2**, since this PS proved to be the most effective in our *in vitro* system. To evaluate this, HeLa cells were subjected to lethal treatment (3×10^{-6} M; 1 and 10 min) and sublethal treatment (3×10^{-8} M; 1 and 10 min) of OPE-Mannose **2**.

Figure 4. ROS generation in HeLa cells after being submitted to PDT with 3×10^{-8} M; 1 and 10 min of irradiation (sublethal treatment) and 3×10^{-6} M; 1 and 10 min of irradiation (lethal treatment) of OPE-mannose **2**. This led to the evaluation of the fluorescent signal of the DCF that appears in the cytoplasm of the cells as a result of oxidation of the DCFH-DA probe. Scale bar: 20 μ m.

As shown in Figure 4, the basal level of DCF-sensitive ROS in HeLa control cells (Figure 4, Control) was not detectable, whereas a significant generation of ROS was observed after 1 min of blue light irradiation at both concentrations. The fluorescent signal was increased at longer irradiation time (10 min) also at both concentrations. The fluorescent signal drastically increases with the concentration of OPE-2 and with the irradiation time, being able to correlate the appearance of ROS with an increase in cell death. Therefore, we can conclude that ROS generation in the cytoplasm of HeLa cells subject to PDT-OPE-Mannose 2 is the key element for cellular cytotoxicity.

Morphological studies

The morphological studies were conducted under sublethal treatments for the HeLa cells. The conditions selected were: (i) OPE-Glucose 1 (3×10^{-7} M) (ii) OPE-Mannose 2 (3×10^{-8} M) and (iii) OPE-Maltose 3 (5×10^{-6} M) with irradiation times between 1 and 10 minutes under blue light (Figure 5).

Figure 5. Photodynamic activity at sublethal treatments with OPE-compounds on HeLa cell line. Cells were incubated for 18 h in the presence of OPE-Glucose 1 (3×10^{-7} M), OPE-Mannose 2 (3×10^{-8} M), and OPE-Maltose 3 (5×10^{-6} M) and subjected to blue light irradiation for variable times. Each point corresponds to the mean value \pm SD from three different experiments.

The analysis of possible morphological alterations in HeLa cells was performed by Toluidine Blue staining 24 h after PDT and are shown in Figure 6. In the case of OPE-glucose **1**, the irradiation times were 3-10 min of irradiation (Figure 6A), 10-15 minutes for OPE-mannose **2** (Figure 6B) and 1-5 minutes for OPE-maltose **3** (Figure 6C). As can be seen in Figure 6, the cells showed significant morphological alterations such as cytoplasmic retraction, vacuolization and loss of adhesion to the substrate. Furthermore, morphologies compatible with necrotic cell death were also observed in most of the cell population such as loss of membrane integrity and formation of membrane spikes. These results strongly suggest that PDT with sublethal doses of OPEs, generate in HeLa cells, cell death by necrosis.

Figure 6. Morphological alterations induced by PDT with sublethal doses of A) OPE-Glucose **1** (3×10^{-7} M); B) OPE-Mannose **2** (3×10^{-8} M) and C) OPE-Maltose **3** (5×10^{-6} M) in HeLa cells. Control cells and cells incubated with OPEs in the dark (Dark), showed an unaffected morphology. Squared expanded images details in each case are from marked black arrowheads cells. Scale bar: 50 μ m.

In order to corroborate the cell death data obtained from the AT staining assays, a study of nuclear morphology by DAPI staining for DNA visualization in HeLa cells subjected to PDT, was carried out under the same treatment conditions as in the morphological study. Well-known morphological

criteria⁴⁰ were used for identification of apoptotic and necrotic cells. Nuclear morphology analysis, performed 24 h after PDT is shown in Figure 7. Under normal conditions, HeLa cells have uniform oval nuclei with condensed chromatin, as can be seen in Control (HeLa cells with no PS) and drug-control cells (HeLa cells incubated with OPEs in the dark). However, when HeLa cells treated with the corresponding OPEs were subjected to PDT, nuclear alterations compatible with necrosis, such as uniform chromatin condensation leading to pyknotic nuclei or degraded chromatin without condensation were observed (Figure 7A, B and C). Non-condensing degraded chromatin is related to necrotic cell death and this is characterized by a homogeneous blue DAPI stain as a result of random cutting in the chromatin.⁴¹

Figure 7. Nuclear Morphological alterations induced by PDT with sublethal doses of OPEs. (A) OPE-Glucose 1 (3×10^{-7} M), (B) OPE-Mannose 2 (3×10^{-8} M) and (C) OPE-Maltose 3 (5×10^{-6} M). Control cells (Control) and cells incubated with OPEs in the dark (Dark), showed a chromatin structure unaffected (yellow arrow in Control and Dark). In all treatment, cells showed typical characteristics of death by necrosis such as condensed chromatin, scattered nucleus content as a result of membrane rupture, non-condensing degraded chromatin, as well as dispersed nucleus content as a result of cell lysis, which is common in necrotic cells. Squared expanded details in each case are from marked yellow arrowheads cells. Scale bar: 50 μ m

Results obtained with nuclear staining with DAPI showed that HeLa cells treated with sublethal doses of OPEs generate a necrotic cell death at all analyzed times. This process of cell death is dependent on the illumination time, since longer irradiation times (between 5 and 15 min) increase the percentage of cells dead by necrosis.

Conclusions

In summary, we efficiently synthesized two new amino-OPEs dyes possessing the mannose and maltose decorations at the chain extremities by an operational simple protocol. The new dyes, together with the corresponding glucose derivative, readily internalized in cancer cells, showing a Golgi or lysosome localization depending on the different sugar structure. Their incubation in the dark did not produce any cell death at the concentration used, whereas the PDT under blue light irradiation (at 450 nm) resulted in a very strong photodynamic effect, due to the production of ROS that induced tumor cell death by necrosis. These results pave the way for the not yet reported use of glycosyl amino OPEs in superficial blue-light induced photodynamic therapy.

Acknowledgments

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Experimental

Chemicals. Solvents were purified according to standard procedures. All the reactions were monitored by TLC on commercially available precoated plates (silica gel 60 F254), and the products were visualized with an acidic methanolic solution of vanillin [1 g dissolved in MeOH (60 mL) and

conc. H₂SO₄ (0.6 mL)] and/or UV lamp. Silica gel 60 was used for column chromatography. Proton (¹H) and carbon (¹³C) NMR spectra were recorded on a Varian 500 spectrometer (at 500 MHz for ¹H; and 125 MHz for ¹³C) using CDCl₃ or dmsO-d₆ as solvents. Chemical shifts are given in parts per million (ppm) (δ relative to residual solvent peak for ¹H and ¹³C), coupling constants (J) are given in hertz, and the attributions are supported by heteronuclear single-quantum coherence (HSQC) and correlation spectroscopy (COSY) experiments. Chemical shifts are reported in ppm relative to CDCl₃ (δ 7.26 ppm) or dmsO-d₆ (2.49 ppm). Melting points were obtained in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Combustion analyses were carried out on a FISON EA1108 elemental analyzer.

CHEMISTRY

Compound 7a. **5a** (1.93 g, 5.00 mmol, 1 eq.), 1,4-diiodo-2,5-dimethoxybenzene **6** (3.90 g, mmol, 2 eq.) and Pd(PPh₃)₄ (0.67 g, 0.60 mmol, 0.12 eq.) were dissolved in dry DMF (40 mL). To the mixture Et₃N (4 mL) was slowly added. The mixture was heated at 60 °C and maintained under continuous stirring and under Ar atmosphere for 3h, until the disappearance of **5a** by TLC. After evaporation of the solvents, the excess of unreacted **6** was separated through precipitation from methanol. Column chromatography of the obtained crude was performed with hexane/EtOAc 70:30 as eluant, and compound **7a** was obtained as a transparent oil (2.17 g, 3.25 mmol, 65%). TLC: R_f = 0.64 (hexane/EtOAc 60:40). ¹H NMR: δ δ 7.27 (s, 1H, H-6), 6.85 (s, 1H, H-3), 5.38 (dd, J_{2',3'} = 3.4, J_{3',4'} = 10.3, 1H, H-3'), 5.31 (m, 2H, H-2',4'), 5.11 (d, J_{1',2'} = 1.5, 1H, H-1'), 4.52 (s, 2H, CH₂C≡), 4.28 and 4.11 (m AB system, J_{5',6'A} = 4.9, J_{5',6'B} = 2.4, J_{6'A,6'B} = 12.3, 2H, H₂-6'), 4.08 (m, 1H, H-5'), 3.83 and 3.82 (two s, 6H, 2 x OCH₃), 2.15, 2.09, 2.03 and 1.99 (4 s, 12H, 4 x CH₃CO). ¹³C NMR: δ δ 170.6, 169.9, 169.8 and 169.6 (4 x CO), 154.7 (C-5), 152.2 (C-2), 122.2 (C-6), 115.3 (C-3), 111.7 (C-4), 96.4 (C-1'), 88.2 (C-1), 87.3 and 83.0 (C≡C), 69.5, 69.0, 68.9 and 66.0 (C-2'-5'), 62.3 (C-6'), 57.0, 56.5 and 56.0 (2 x OCH₃, CH₂C≡), 20.9, 20.7 and 20.6 (4 x CH₃CO). Anal. Calcd for C₂₅H₂₉IO₁₂ (648.40): C, 46.31; H, 4.51. Found: C, 46.43; H, 4.50.

Compound 7b. **5b** (3.50 g, 5.19 mmol, 1 eq.), 1,4-diiodo-2,5-dimethoxybenzene **6** (4.05 g, 10.38 mmol, 2 eq.) and Pd(PPh₃)₄ (0.72 g, 0.62 mmol, 0.12 eq.) were dissolved in dry DMF (42 mL). To

the mixture Et₃N (42 mL) was slowly added. The mixture was heated at 60 °C and maintained under continuous stirring and under Ar atmosphere for 3h, until the disappearance of **5b** by TLC. After evaporation of the solvents, the excess of unreacted **6** was separated through precipitation from methanol. Column chromatography of the crude obtained from evaporation of the mother liquors was performed with hexane/EtOAc 60:40 as eluant, and compound **7b** was obtained as a with solid (2.88 g, 3.08 mmol, 59%). TLC: R_f=0.58 (hexane/EtOAc 40:60). Mp 121-123 °C. ¹H NMR: δ δ 7.28 (s, 1H, H-6), 6.84 (s, 1H, H-3), 5.39 (d, J_{1'',2''}=4.0, 1H, H-1''), 5.33 (t, J_{2'',3''} = J_{3'',4''} = 10.0, 1H, H-3''), 5.27 (t, J_{2',3'} = J_{3',4'} = 8.8, 1H, H-3'), 5.03 (t, J_{3'',4''} = J_{4'',5''} = 10.0, 1H, H-4''), 4.88 (t, J_{1',2'} = J_{2',3'} = 8.8, 1H, H-2'), 4.86 - 4.82 (m, 2H, H-1'',2''), 4.58 (s, 2H, CH₂C≡), 4.23, 4.11 and 4.02 (two m AB system, one m, 5H, H₂-6', H₂-6'', H-4'), 3.94 (m, 1H, H-5''), 3.83 and 3.82 (two s, 6H, 2 x OCH₃), 3.72 (m, 1H, H-5'), 2.11, 2.08, 2.02, 2.00, 1.99, 1.98 and 1.97 (7 s, 21H, 7 x CH₃CO). ¹³C NMR: δ δ 170.5, 170.4, 170.2, 169.9, 169.7 and 169.3 (7 x CO), 154.9 (C-5), 152.3 (C-2), 122.2 (C-6), 115.1 (C-3), 111.8 (C-4), 97.6 (C-1'), 95.5 (C-1''), 88.3 and 83.1 (C≡C), 87.3 (C-1), 75.4, 72.6, 72.2, 71.9, 70.0, 69.2, 68.5 and 68.0 (C-2'-5', C-2''-5''), 62.7 and 61.4 (C-6', C-6''), 57.0, 56.9 and 56.5 (2 x OCH₃, CH₂C≡), 20.9, 20.8 and 20.6 (4 x CH₃CO). Anal. Calcd for C₃₇H₄₅IO₂₀ (936,65): C, 47.45; H, 4.84. Found: C, 47.56; H, 4.83.

Compound 10a. To a flask Pd(PPh₃)₄ (0.40 g, 0.35 mmol, 0.15 eq.), **7a** (1.50 g, 2.31 mmol, 2 eq.) and **8** (0.20 g, 1.16 mmol, 1 eq.) were added; the flask was capped with a rubber septum and evacuated. After backfilling with N₂ - this process was repeated three times- dry DMF (18 mL) and Et₃N (18 mL) were added at room temperature. The reaction mixture was heated at 60°C, and maintained under continuous stirring for 4h, until the disappearance of the starting compounds by TLC (hexane/EtOAc 40:60). Solvents were removed under reduced pressure and the reaction crude was purified by column chromatography on silica gel, using hexane/EtOAc (up to 50:50) as eluant, giving compound **10a** as a yellow solid (1.08 g, 0.89 mmol, 77%). TLC: R_f=0.36 (hexane/EtOAc 40:60). Mp 109-111 °C. ¹H NMR: δ 7.48 (d, J_{5,6} = 8.5, 1H, H-6), 7.08 (m, 2H, H-3, 5), 7.00, 6.98, 6.97 and 6.95 (four s, 4H, 2 x H-3',6'), 5.39 (dd, J_{2'',3''} = 3.5, J_{3'',4''} = 10.0, 2H, 2 x H-3''), 5.33 (m, 4H,

2 x H-2",4"), 5.14 (d, $J_{1'',2''} = 1.5$, 2H, 2 x H-1"), 4.56 (s, 4H, 2 x $\text{CH}_2\text{C}\equiv$), 4.30-4.13 (m AB system, $J_{5'',6''\text{A}}=5$, $J_{5'',6''\text{B}} = 2.5$, $J_{6''\text{A},6''\text{B}} = 12.5$, 4H, 2 x H₂-6"), 4.10 (m, 2H, 2 x H-5"), 3.89, 3.88, 3.86 and 3.85 (four s, 12H, 4 x OCH₃), 3.03 [s, 6H, N(CH₃)₂], 2.17, 2.10, 2.05 and 2.00 (four s, 24H, 8 x CH₃CO). ¹³C NMR: δ δ 170.6, 169.9, 169.8 and 169.7 (8 x CO), 154.4, 154.0, 153.9 and 153.8 (C-2, 2 x C-2',5'), 134.3 (C-6), 123.7(C-4), 123.6 (C-5), 120.0 (C-3), 115.9, 115.7, 115.5 and 115.0 (2 x C-3',6'), 115.1, 114.4, 113.7, 112.1 and 111.8 (C-1, 2 x C-1',4'), 96.4 (2 x C-1"), 95.4, 94.6, 92.7, 88.9, 88.8, 86.6, 83.5 and 83.4 (4 x C≡C), 69.5, 69.2, 69.0 and 66.1 (2 x C-2"- 5"), 62.3 (2 x C-6"), 56.5, 56.3 and 56.0 (2 x $\text{CH}_2\text{C}\equiv$ and 4 x OCH₃), 43.4 [N(CH₃)₂], 20.9, 20.7 and 20.6 (8 x CH_3CO). Anal. Calcd for C₆₂H₆₇NO₂₄ (1210.19): C, 61.53; H, 5.58; N, 1.16. Found: C, 61.37; H, 5.59; N, 1.16.

Compound 10b. To a flask Pd(PPh₃)₄ (0.40 g, 0.35 mmol, 0.15 eq.), **7b** (2.16 g, 2.31 mmol, 2 eq.) and **8** (0.20 g, 1.16 mmol, 1 eq.) were added; the flask was capped with a rubber septum and evacuated. After backfilling with N₂ - this process was repeated three times - dry DMF (18 mL) and Et₃N (18 mL) were added at room temperature. The reaction mixture was heated at 60°C, and maintained under continuous stirring for 4 h, until the disappearance of the starting compounds by TLC (hexane/EtOAc 60:40). Solvents were removed under reduced pressure and the reaction crude was purified by chromatography on silica gel, using hexane/EtOAc (40:60) as eluent, giving compound **10b** as a yellow solid (1.53 g, 0.85 mmol, 74%). TLC: R_f = 0.42 (hexane/EtOAc 30:70). Mp 140-142 °C. ¹H NMR: δ 7.47 (d, $J_{5,6} = 8.5$, 1H, H-6), 7.09 (m, 2H, H-3, 5), 7.02, 7.00, 6.95 and 6.94 (four s, 4H, 2 x H-3',6'), 5.42 (d, $J_{1''',2'''} = 3.5$, 2H, 2 x H-1'''), 5.36 and 5.30 (2t, $J_{\text{ax-ax}} = 10.0$, $J_{\text{ax-ax}} = 9.0$, 4H, 2 x H-3'', 2xH-3'''), 5.04 (t, $J_{3'',4''} = J_{4'',5''} = 10.0$, 2H, 2 x H-4''), 4.92 - 4.84 (m, 6H, 2 x H-1'',2'',2'''), 4.63 (s, 4H, 2 x $\text{CH}_2\text{C}\equiv$), 4.51, 4.24 and 4.04 (m, 10H, 2 x H₂-6'', 6''', H-4''), 3.95 (m, 2H, 2 x H-5''), 3.90, 3.88, and 3.87 (three s, 12H, 4 x OCH₃), 3.75 (m, 2H, 2 x H-5''), 3.04 [s, 6H, N(CH₃)₂], 2.13, 2.10, 2.04, 2.02, 2.01 and 2.00 (six s, 42H, 14 x CH₃CO). ¹³C NMR: δ δ 170.5, 170.4, 170.2, 169.9, 169.7 and 169.4 (14 x CO), 154.4, 154.1, 153.9 and 153.8 (C-2, 2 x C-2',5'), 134.3 (C-6), 123.7 (C-4), 123.6 and 120.0 (C-3,5), 115.8, 115.5, and 115.0 (2 x C-3',6'), 115.2, 114.4, 113.8, 112.2 and 111.9 (C-1, 2 x C-1',4'), 97.8 (2 x C-1''), 95.5 (2 x C-1'''), 95.5, 94.6, 92.6, 89.0, 88.9, 86.6, 83.5

and 83.4 (4 x C≡C), 75.4, 72.6, 72.2, 71.9, 70.0, 69.3, 68.5 and 68.0 (2 x C-2"-5", 2 x C-2'''-5'''), 62.7 and 61.5 (2 x C-6", 6'''), 57.0, 56.5 and 56.3 (2 x $\underline{\text{CH}_2\text{C}\equiv}$ and 4 x OCH₃), 43.4 [N(CH₃)₂], 20.9, 20.8, 20.7 and 20.5 (14 x $\underline{\text{CH}_3\text{CO}}$). Anal. Calcd for C₈₆H₉₉NO₄₀ (1786.69): C, 57.81; H, 5.58; N, 0.78. Found: C, 57.88; H, 5.59; N, 0.78.

General Procedure for quantitative deacetylation. The starting product (0.2 mmol) was dissolved in THF/MeOH (1:1, 40 mL). To this mixture a large excess of aqueous ammonia (12 mL) was added and the reaction was then maintained under continuous stirring at room temperature overnight, until the disappearance of the starting product by TLC. Solvents were removed under reduced pressure and the undesired acetamide was eliminated by a series of Et₂O washings of the obtained solid.

OPE-Mannose 2. It was obtained following procedure starting from **10a** (0.50 g, 0.41 mmol), as a yellow solid (0.34 g, 0.39 mmol, 97%). TLC: R_f=0.05 (CHCl₃/MeOH 80:20). Mp 217-219 °C. ¹H NMR (dms-*d*6): δ 7.44 (d, *J*_{5,6} = 8.0, 1H, H-6), 7.16, 7.10, 7.09 and 7.08 (four s, 4H, 2 x H-3',6'), 7.01 (m, 2H, H-3,5), 4.87 (bs, 2H, 2 x H-1''), 4.83 (d, *J*_{vic}=4.5, 2H, 2 x OH), 4.75 (d, *J*_{vic}=5.0, 2H, 2 x OH), 4.62 (d, *J*_{vic}=6.0, 2H, 2 x OH), 4.53 - 4.43 (m, 6H, 2 x CH₂C≡, 2 x OH), 3.82, 3.81 and 3.80 (three s, 12H, 4 x OCH₃), 3.71 - 3.34 (m, 12H, 2 x H₂"-6''), 2.98 [s, 6H, N(CH₃)₂]. ¹³C NMR (dms-*d*6): δ 154.0, 153.7, 153.6, 153.4 and 153.3 (C-2, 2 x C-2',5'), 134.4 (C-6), 123.3 (C-4), 122.7 and 119.2 (C-3,5), 115.8, 115.7, 115.5 and 114.9 (2 x C-3',6'), 113.7, 113.1, 112.4, 112.0 and 111.8 (C-1, 2 x C-1',4'), 98.3 (2 x C-1''), 94.8, 94.3, 92.7, 91.1, 91.0, 87.2, 82.1, and 82.0 (4 x C≡C), 74.4, 70.9, 70.1 and 66.9 (2 x C-2"-5''), 61.1 (2 x C-6''), 56.3, 56.2 and 56.1 (4 x OCH₃), 53.8 (2 x $\underline{\text{CH}_2\text{C}\equiv}$), 42.7 [N(CH₃)₂]. Anal. Calcd for C₄₆H₅₁NO₁₆ (873.89): C, 63.22; H, 5.88; N, 1.60. Found: C, 63.33; H, 5.89; N, 1.60.

OPE-Maltose 3. It was obtained following procedure starting from **10b** (0.73 g, 0.41 mmol), as a yellow solid (0.49 g, 0.40 mmol, 99%). TLC: R_f=0.05 (CHCl₃/MeOH 80:20). Mp 224-226 °C. ¹H NMR: δ δ 7.45 (d, *J*_{5,6} = 8.5, 1H, H-6), 7.18, 7.12, 7.09 and 7.08 (four s, 4H, 2 x H-3',6'), 7.03 (m, 2H, H-3, 5), 5.53 (d, *J*_{vic}=3.5, 2H, 2 x OH), 5.42 (d, *J*_{vic}=6.5, 2H, 2 x OH), 5.27 (d, *J*_{vic}=5.0, 2H, 2 x OH), 5.03 (d, *J*_{1'',2'''}=4.0, 2H, 2 x H-1'''), 4.90 (d, *J*_{vic}=5.5, 2H, 2 x OH), 4.88 (d, *J*_{vic}=5.0, 2H, 2 x OH),

4.70 - 4.50 (m, 6H, 2 x CH₂C≡, 2 x OH-6"), 4.38 (d, $J_{1,2} = 8.0$, 2H, 2 x H-1"), 3.83, 3.82, and 3.81 (three s, 12H, 4 x OCH₃), 3.78 – 3.04 (m, 12H, 2 x H-2"-6", 2 x H-2'''-6'''), 2.99 [s, 6H, N(CH₃)₂]. ¹³C NMR: δ δ 154.0, 153.7 and 153.4 (C-2, 2 x C-2',5'), 134.4 (C-6), 123.3 (C-4), 122.7 and 119.2 (C-3,5), 115.8, 115.6 and 114.9 (2 x C-3',6'), 113.7, 113.1, 112.4, 112.3 and 111.9 (C-1, 2 x C-1',4'), 101.0 and 100.7 (2 x C-1", 1'''), 94.8, 94.2, 92.7, 91.2, 91.1, 87.2, 82.2 and 82.1 (4 x C≡C), 79.5, 76.4, 75.3, 73.4, 73.2, 72.8, 72.4 and 69.9 (2 x C-2"- 5", 2 x C-2'''- 5'''), 60.8 and 60.7 (2 x C-6", 6'''), 56.3, 56.2, 56.1 and 56.0 (2 x CH₂C≡ and 4 x OCH₃), 42.7 [N(CH₃)₂]. Anal. Calcd for C₅₈H₇₁NO₂₆ (1198.18): C, 58.14; H, 5.97; N, 1.17. Found: C, 58.07; H, 5.99; N, 1.17.

Cell culture

The HeLa human cervical cancer cells (ATCC) were grown as a monolayer employing Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (DMEM) containing 10% fetal calf serum (FCS) and 50 units/mL penicillin and 50 µg/mL streptomycin (Fisher). The cells were incubated at 37 °C in a humidified 5% CO atmosphere and the medium was changed daily. For the photocytotoxicity experiments, cells were plated on 24-well plates and for fluorescence observation, cells were plated onto coverslips placed into 6-wells plates.

Intracellular localization of each sugars-conjugates OPEs

The cells were seeded onto coverslips placed into 6-well plate and allow to grow for 48 h. After that, cells were incubated with each sugars-conjugates OPEs for 24 h. The samples were washed twice with PBS and then were mounted onto slides with PBS. Samples were studied under fluorescence microscopy using an Olympus BX61 microscope with an Olympus DP70 digital camera.

Photodynamic therapy treatment *in vitro*

Cells seeded in 24-well plates were incubated 18 h with an appropriate volume of each sugars-conjugates OPEs. After that, irradiations with blue light (450nm) were performed. After irradiations,

the medium was replaced by fresh complete medium without drugs and the cells were incubated in dark for another 24 h and then tested their viability.

MTT viability assay

Phototoxicity and cell viability were documented by the MTT assay. Following the appropriate treatments 3[4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl]-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium-bromide (MTT) solution was added to each well at a concentration of 0.5 ng/mL, and plates were incubated at 37 °C for 2 h. The resulting formazan crystals were dissolved by the addition of DMSO and absorbance was measured at 542 nm. The same procedure was carried out without irradiation for determining dark toxicity.

Determination of intracellular ROS production

Determination of ROS production was performed as described.⁴² After 18 hours of sugars-conjugates OPEs treatments, 2,7-dichloro- dihydrofluorescein diacetate (DHF-DA; Sigma) was added to cell cultures to a final concentration of 10^{-5} M and incubated 1 hour. Cells were then subjected to irradiation as described and fixed with a 3.7% formaldehyde solution in PBS for 15-20 minutes at room temperature. Cells were observed in a fluorescence microscope for ROS detection through DCF emission (exc= 436 nm).

Cell morphology

Changes in cell morphology were analyzed using bright field illumination. After PDT treatments the cells were fixed with cold methanol for 7 min. After three washes with PBS, cells were stained with toluidine blue (TB, Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) (0.5 mg/mL in distilled water, 5 min). After being washed and air-dried, preparations were mounted in Toluène (Fisher chemical) and observed under bright field illumination.

Dapi Staining

At different times after treatments, cells on coverslips were fixed in cold methanol for 7 min, air dried and stained with Dapi (300 nM in PBS) for 1 min. Preparations were mounted in Toluène (Fisher chemical) and observed by fluorescence microscopy under UV excitation. Well-known morphological criteria were used to assess necrotic and apoptotic cells^{40,41}.

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